

Scaling up the formation of agents with heterogeneous sensing: mixed distance and bearing-only

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Abstract—Unlike the case with identical neighboring agents whose actions are mirrored, the problem of distributed formation control design with heterogeneous sensing is not straightforward. This paper considers the problem of distributed formation control where each agent can only control distances or bearings with its neighbors. We firstly develop a rigidity theory with heterogeneous sensing to ensure that the desired shape is well-posed. Secondly, we propose an iterative method that allows us to scale up the number of agents with heterogeneous sensing. Finally, we show the effectiveness of our method by numerical simulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Distributed formation control is one of the most actively studied topics in multi-agent systems [1]. Among its many potential applications, it is one of the key elements towards the yet unsolved problem of realizing reliable and predictable robot swarms [2]. The most popular design technique for distributed formation controllers is based on the gradient descent of potential functions that seek to minimize the sum of inter-agent geometry errors, which can be defined based on distances [3], bearings [4], or inner angles [5], in order to achieve prescribed *formation shapes* [6]–[9].

In the literature on formation control, the use of homogeneous sensing mechanism for each agent is ubiquitous. In this case, all agents maintain the same type of geometrical constraints, e.g., distance or bearing, with their neighboring agents [1]. Having two neighboring agents sharing the same formation controller is mathematically convenient for the stability analysis of the multi-agent systems, where the inherent symmetry can be exploited in the analysis. However, there is a lack of methodologies for scaling up formations where neighboring agents control different geometric variables. In this paper, we propose a systematic and iterative method to scale the number of agents while alternating the controlled geometric variable for the new agent that joins the formation network. In our method, the new agent needs to calculate the gains for new created edges to its neighbors. The computation resources required for calculating gains grows cubic with the number of agents, i.e., the calculation of the minimum

eigenvalue of a $(n + 1)$ square matrix, ensuring our method highly applicable.

There are few works in literature that investigate such mixed constraints or heterogeneous sensing case. The paper [10] focuses on the combination of distance and bearing constraints that are defined in an undirected graph. Such an assumption entails that for a pair of neighboring agents, both agents control the same geometry. In this paper, we relax such an assumption, whereby for one pair of neighboring agents, one agent can control either the distance or the bearing between them. The authors in [11] consider the combination of distance, bearing and angle constraints at the same time, encompassing a general concept for *rigidity*; still, as in [10] the neighboring agents have symmetrical control actions for the same edge in the graph.

When neighboring agents control the same geometrical variable, it can restrict their application. Firstly, mirrored control actions typically demand neighboring robots to be equipped with the same type and quality of sensors. Definitively, different sensing mechanisms can break the symmetry execution expected by the control design. Secondly, certain robots may have neighboring robots that can only work with different geometrical constraints, e.g., distance constraint with one neighbor and bearing one with another neighbor. In this case, the robot must be equipped with multiple types of sensors. Thirdly, in unstructured environments, the sensing measurement may become less accurate in certain conditions. Let us provide two specific examples to illustrate the applicability of our approach. Firstly, we can use our method to check whether an agent can switch between sensing modes based on its initial distance to neighbors. For example, if our approach guarantees stability for both sensing modes at all times, then a merging agent can use bearing-based sensing when it is far from other agents and switch to distance-based sensing when it is close to its neighbors. Secondly, we can evaluate the impact of an agent on the robustness of formation by determining whether the desired shape remains stable regardless of the type of sensor used by that agent. If the formation shape remains stable regardless of the sensor type, then that agent can safely switch sensing mechanisms if one sensor systems fail. Otherwise, neighboring agents may need to switch their sensing mechanisms simultaneously to prevent instability in the formation shape. To guarantee stability across the entire network, we may need to evaluate all possible combinations of edges/sensing in the heterogeneous network.

This paper addresses the formation control problem con-

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sidering heterogeneous sensing between neighboring agents. More precisely, each neighboring agent controls inter-agent distances or bearings exclusively. Such problem has initially been studied in [12], where the authors analyzed the stability of the two and three-agent cases rigorously. Different from [12], in this work, we explore and analyze the stability of merging heterogeneous neighboring agents into an existing (stable) heterogeneous formation that provides a method to scale up the number of agents. In particular, we provide a sufficient condition of the control gain for the new edges to guarantee the stability of the formation. Such results are based on the following two novel notions: (i). the heterogeneous sensing rigidity for defining the desired shape of a heterogeneous sensing formation; and (ii). the heterogeneous persistence for dealing with the interaction between a pair of heterogeneous neighboring agents. These conditions imply that scaling up the formation requires both the heterogeneous persistence and properly chosen control gains for the newly defined edges. Numerical simulations shows the effectiveness of our method.

This paper is organized as follows. We first present the required preliminaries in Section II. In Section III, we use heterogeneous sensing rigidity to define the desired formation shape and introduce the concept of heterogeneous-sensing-persistent formation to guarantee that our formation has a feasible solution. Then, in the Section IV, we propose the formation control law dealing with neighboring agents with heterogeneous sensing, and we show how to merge newly heterogeneous agents to the existing formation. Numerical simulations are presented in Section V for illustrating merging case with six agents. Finally, conclusions are presented in Section VI.

II. PRELIMINARIES AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Graph theory

A directed/undirected graph \mathcal{G} is defined by the tuple $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, where $\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is the *vertex* set and $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ is the *edge* set with $m = |\mathcal{E}|$ number of edges. If $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$, the ordered pair (i, j) refers to the edge whose direction is represented by an arrow with node i as the tail and node j as the head. We assume throughout the paper that there is no self-loop in the considered graph \mathcal{G} , i.e., $(i, i) \notin \mathcal{E}$ for all $i \in \mathcal{V}$. The set of neighbors of vertex i is denoted by $\mathcal{N}_i \triangleq \{j \in \mathcal{V} \mid (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}\}$.

B. Distributed formation control law

Given a finite collection of n points $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^n$ in \mathbb{R}^d with $n \geq 2$ and $d \in \{2, 3\}$, a configuration is denoted as $p = [p_1^\top, \dots, p_n^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{dn}$, where $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ represents the position of agent i . Whenever it is clear from the context, the i -th robot is labeled as Ri . A framework in \mathbb{R}^d , denoted as $\mathcal{G}(p)$, is a combination of an undirected graph $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ and a configuration p , where vertex $i \in \mathcal{V}$ in the graph is mapped to the point p_i in the configuration. We assume $p_i \neq p_j$ if $i \neq j$, i.e., two agents can not be at the same position. For points $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $p_j \in \mathbb{R}^d$ of the formation, we define the relative position vector as $z_{ij} = p_j - p_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the distance as

$d_{ij} = \|z_{ij}\| \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ and the relative bearing as $g_{ij} = \frac{z_{ij}}{d_{ij}} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, all relative to a global coordinate frame Σ^g .

An important methodology for studying and designing multi-agent formation control is the *rigidity theory* that connects geometrical and graph properties of the desired formation shape. Two rigidity concepts are widely studied for the past decades, *distance-based rigidity theory* [13] and the *bearing-only based rigidity theory* [4], [14]. Based on these two rigid concepts, researchers have proposed various distributed distance-based [15] and bearing-only [16] formation control laws. In the context of these two main formation control, we design our distance-based and bearing-only control in the following.

Using the framework $\mathcal{G}(p)$ as defined before, we assume that each agent position p_i evolves in \mathbb{R}^d according to

$$\dot{p}_i = u_i, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, n\} \quad (1)$$

for all $i = 1, \dots, n$, where $u_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the velocity control input. As before, we denote the concatenated control input by $u = [u_1^\top \ \dots \ u_n^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{nd}$.

1) *Distance-based formation control*: For a framework $\mathcal{G}(p)$ with only distance-based agents, we can design a distance-based formation control based on the distance rigidity framework. Let us denote $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{V}^{\text{dist}}, \mathcal{E}^{\text{dist}})$ as the undirected graph for $\mathcal{G}(p)$, where $\mathcal{V}^{\text{dist}}$ and $\mathcal{E}^{\text{dist}}$ represent the vertex set and the ordered edge set, respectively. Let $d \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}^{\text{dist}}|}$ be the vector containing the desired distances and define the distance formation error in the l -th edge $e_l^{\text{dist}} = \|z_l\|^2 - d_l^2$. Suppose that for every edge l , V_l is a positive semi-definite function of e_l^{dist} such that $V_l^{\text{dist}}(e_l^{\text{dist}}) = 0 \Leftrightarrow e_l^{\text{dist}} = 0$, which implies that the edge distance is equal to the desired one when V_l^{dist} is at its minimum. Accordingly, the corresponding gradient-based control law for each agent i is given by

$$u_i^{\text{dist}} = - \sum_{\{l \mid (i,j) \in \mathcal{E}^{\text{dist}}\}} k_l \frac{\partial V_l^{\text{dist}}(e_l^{\text{dist}})}{\partial p_i}^\top,$$

where $\mathcal{E}_l^{\text{dist}}$ denotes the l -th edge in the set $\mathcal{E}^{\text{dist}}$ and $k_l > 0$ is an associated control gain. In this paper, we will study a particular distance-based potential function defined by $V_l^{\text{dist}} = \frac{k_l (e_l^{\text{dist}})^2}{4d_l^2}$, which gives us the following local control law

$$u_i^{\text{dist}} = - \sum_{\{l \mid (i,j) \in \mathcal{E}_l^{\text{dist}}\}} k_l e_l^{\text{dist}} \frac{z_l}{2d_l^2}. \quad (2)$$

Note that the above control law is the distance-based formation control law which guarantees exponential stability due to the use of quadratic potential function V_l^{dist} as also studied in [15].

2) *Bearing-only formation control*: Similar to the distance-based formation control above, using the bearing-only based rigid frameworks, the desired formation shape is defined by a set of inter-agent bearing constraints. Let us denote $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{V}^{\text{bearing}}, \mathcal{E}^{\text{bearing}})$ as the undirected graph for $\mathcal{G}(p)$, where $\mathcal{V}^{\text{bearing}}$ and $\mathcal{E}^{\text{bearing}}$ represent the vertex set and the ordered edge set, respectively. Let $g^* \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{E}^{\text{bearing}}|}$ define the desired bearing for all edges in $\mathcal{E}^{\text{bearing}}$. Let us define the bearing error at the l -th edge by $e_l^{\text{bearing}} = g_l - g_l^*$.

We will now define the corresponding potential function V that can be used in the gradient control as in (2). For each edge l with the associated agent pair (i, j) , we consider the following local potential function $V_l^{\text{bearing}}(z_l, e_l^{\text{bearing}}) = k_l \|z_l^*\| \|z_l\| \|e_l^{\text{bearing}}\|^2$, where $\|z_l^*\|$ is a positive constant, which is determined by the desired shape, helping to adjust the magnitude of the control inputs. Note that for bearing-only formations, we could choose $\|z_l^*\| = 1$ for all edges. It is obvious that $V_l^{\text{bearing}} \geq 0$ and $V_l^{\text{bearing}}(e_l^{\text{bearing}}) = 0 \iff e_l^{\text{bearing}} = 0 \iff g_l = g_l^*$. Despite V_l^{bearing} has a dependence on both z_l and e_l^{bearing} , the corresponding bearing-only gradient control law for an agent pair (i, j) does not depend on z_l and it is given by

$$\begin{aligned} u_i^{\text{bearing}} &= - \sum_{\{l|(i,j)=\mathcal{E}_l^{\text{bearing}}\}} k_l \frac{\partial V_l^{\text{bearing}}(z_l, e_l^{\text{bearing}})}{\partial p_i} \\ &= \sum_{\{l|(i,j)=\mathcal{E}_l^{\text{bearing}}\}} k_l \|z_l^*\| e_l^{\text{bearing}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{E}_l^{\text{bearing}}$ denotes the l -th edge in the set $\mathcal{E}^{\text{bearing}}$ and $k_l > 0$ is an associated control gain. Note that this law is a modified version of the bearing-only formation control law (19) as presented in [16]. In comparison to the one used in [16], we introduce a scaling factor to the potential function V_l^{bearing} in each edge l , which does not change the sign property of the function and its time-derivative $\dot{V}_l^{\text{bearing}}$. Therefore, the modified control law still ensures the almost global asymptotic stability of the desired formation shape provided that the formation shape is infinitesimally bearing rigid. This scaling factor is introduced to ensure that the magnitude of the bearing-only and distance-based control inputs are of the same order.

C. Problem Formulation

Based on the background information above, we can now formulate our distributed formation control problem where the neighboring agents use heterogeneous sensing information to maintain the formation.

Let us consider two heterogeneous agent sets $\mathcal{V}^{\text{dist}}$ and $\mathcal{V}^{\text{bearing}}$. All agents i in $\mathcal{V}^{\text{dist}}$ are distance-based agents which can only maintain desired distance to their neighbors given by the desired distance set $\bar{d}_i = \{d_{ij}^* > 0 | d_{ij}^* \in \mathbb{R}, j \in \mathcal{N}_i\}$. Each agent $i \in \mathcal{V}^{\text{dist}}$ is able to measure the relative positions with its neighbors in its *local coordinate frame* Σ^i which is not necessarily aligned with *global coordinate frame* Σ^g . On the other hand, all agents i in $\mathcal{V}^{\text{bearing}}$ are bearing-only agents whose goal are to maintain a desired bearing with their neighbors following the desired bearing set $\bar{g}_i = \left\{ g_{ij}^* = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_{ij}^* \\ \sin \theta_{ij}^* \end{bmatrix} | \theta_{ij}^* \in (-\pi, \pi], j \in \mathcal{N}_i \right\}$. Each agent $i \in \mathcal{V}^{\text{bearing}}$ is able to measure the relative bearings with its neighbors in its *local coordinate frame* Σ^i which is aligned with *global coordinate frame* Σ^g .

Distributed formation control with heterogeneous sensing problems: Given the distance-based agents $\mathcal{V}^{\text{dist}}$ with

the associated desired distance constraint set \bar{d}_i and the bearing-only agents $\mathcal{V}^{\text{bearing}}$ with the associated desired bearing constraint set \bar{g}_i :

- Q1. Determine the geometric rigidity properties of the desired formation shape.
- Q2. For each agent i , design a local control law

$$u_i = f_i(z_l, e_l | \forall l \text{ s.t. } (i, j) = \mathcal{E}_l)$$

with Lipschitz continuous f_i and with e_l be either the distance error or bearing error on the l -th edge depending on the agent's type, such that all agents converge to the desired shape (assumed feasible), i.e. $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e_l(t) = 0$ for all l .

- Q3. Given a new agent j to be added to the formation, determine the new formation configuration and local control law u_j for agent j and its neighboring agents such that all agents converge to the newly extended shape without compromising the stability of the global formation.

This paper proposes to answer the three questions. Firstly, to address Q1, the paper introduces the concept of heterogeneous sensing rigidity in Section III. Secondly, the control law (2) and (3) in preliminaries with specific chosen gains satisfy the problem Q2. Finally, in Q3, we focus on the merging problem in heterogeneous sensing formation in which the new agent $l = n + 1$ (either it is a distance or a bearing agent) will join a n -agent stable formation. This paper aims to investigate conditions so that the control laws that meet Q2 can handle the scaling up of the formation.

III. HETEROGENEOUS SENSING

A. Heterogeneous sensing rigidity

Based on the aforementioned problem formulation, we will consider in this section a rigidity graph framework that takes into account multiple sensing mechanism.

Following the standard notion to define rigidity by trivial motion, like [4], [15], *infinitesimally heterogeneous sensing rigidity* [17] provides the condition whether a framework can be uniquely determined up to a translation factor given certain relative bearings and distances between pairs of agents in the framework. Additionally, considering the minimal edges in the framework, $\mathcal{G}(p)$ is called *minimally infinitesimally heterogeneous sensing rigid* if it is infinitesimally rigid and has exactly $2n - 2$ edges.

B. Heterogeneous persistent formation

It is important to note that the notion of rigidity refers to an undirected graph, where two connected agents must maintain the same (distance or bearing-only) constraint. This notion can no longer be applicable when the two connected agents do not share the same constraint to maintain. To ensure there exists a feasible solution p of a set of constraints $F(p) = r^*$ for the desired vector of distance-based and bearing-only constraints, the notion of persistent formation is introduced for the distance-based formation control [18], [19] and for the bearing-only formation [20]. Following the standard notion of persistent formation in these papers, we proceed to use *heterogeneous*

persistent formation [17] to ensure the existence of solution in heterogeneous sensing formation. Additionally, to address the scaling up problem, we propose the concept *minimally heterogeneous persistent* to determine the relationship between Degrees of Freedom (DOFs) and constraints denoted by edges in graph.

Definition 3.1 (minimally heterogeneous persistent): A framework $\mathcal{G}(p)$ is minimally heterogeneous persistent, if it is heterogeneous persistent and has exactly $2n - 2$ edges

Theorem 2.3 in [18] gives the relationship between the global Degrees of Freedom (DOFs) of the whole formation and the local DOFs of each agent. Based on this established relationship, the heterogeneous persistent formation may contain one-leader or two-coleaders in a leader-follower setting, but not more than that¹. Roughly speaking, one-leader formation refers to the formation framework in which there is only an agent (so-called the leader) that has two DOFs (in the desired formation) and all other agents have zero DOF. Similarly, two-coleaders formation corresponds to the formation framework where there are two agents (so-called the coleaders) with one DOF (in the desired formation) and the rest has zero DOF.

In the subsequent section, we present the problem of extending the formation by adding a new agent to the formation framework. Depending on how the new agent interacts with some of the agents in the existing formation, we can classify the merging problem into two different cases:

- C1. Unilateral-connection merging.** In this case, the agents in the original formation can be measured by the merging agent unilaterally and the original graph is extended by one vertex, where newly added edges all start from the added vertex.
- C2. Interconnection merging.** In this case, both the merging agent and some of the existing agents can measure each other. This means that in the extended graph, there is an edge that starts from the new vertex and another edge that ends at the new vertex.

As a consequence of the foregoing discussion, a new agent can only be added to the existing heterogeneous persistent formation while preserving this property if it is connected to the leader or one of the co-leaders of the original graph in the case of C2.

IV. HETEROGENEOUS SENSING FORMATION CONTROL AND MERGING

In this subsection, we study when an agent is added to an existing formation of n heterogeneous sensing agents. In this case, the n heterogeneous sensing agents are able to form a rigid formation with local stability and we investigate methods to allow another agent merging into such stable n -agent system and forming an asymptotically stable $n + 1$ rigid formation shape. It extends the well-known results in homogeneous sensing formation case. If we consider the distance-based agents only or bearing-only agents only, our methodology is the same as the standard homogeneous sensing formation control with directed graph as in [18], [19]. Depending on how

¹We refer interested readers to [18] on a leader-follower setup in distributed formation control problems.

Fig. 1. Interconnection merging into a stable formation with two coleaders; \bullet represents a distance-based agent and \bullet represents a bearing-only agent; dashed circle \bullet represents a merging distance-based agent. Correspondingly, blue dashed arrows are added sensing carried out by the distance-based agents.

the newly added edges are connected to the merging agent, we present three different analysis below, namely, (i). the case when it merges into a stable formation with two coleaders; (ii). the case when it merges into a stable formation with one leader; and (iii). the case when it merges unilaterally to a stable formation (i.e. case C1 as mentioned before).

In the following, we will employ linearization to analyze the stability. To facilitate the analysis, let us recall some key facts and introduce some lemmas that will be useful later. Firstly we denote a pair of unit vectors as $v_i = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha_i \\ \sin \alpha_i \end{bmatrix}$ and $\bar{v}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_i \\ -\cos \alpha_i \end{bmatrix}$. These vectors exhibit following relationship: $v_i^\top \bar{v}_i = \bar{v}_i^\top v_i = 0$, $\bar{v}_i^\top v_j = -\bar{v}_j^\top v_i = \sin(\alpha_i - \alpha_j)$. For each v_i , we can define a projection matrix $P_i = v_i v_i^\top$.

Lemma 4.1: For a linear combination of projection matrices $D = k_i P_i + k_j P_j$ with positive constants k_i and k_j , if $|\sin(\alpha_i - \alpha_j)| \neq 0$ then $\frac{1}{k_i k_j \sin^2(\alpha_i - \alpha_j)} (\bar{v}_i \bar{v}_i^\top + \bar{v}_j \bar{v}_j^\top) =: D^{-1}$ is the inverse matrix of D .

Lemma 4.2: For a given complete graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ and a linear combination of projection matrices $P = \sum_{i=1}^n k_i P_i$ with positive constants $k_i, i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, the eigenvalues of P are given by

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n k_i}{2} \pm \sqrt{\frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n k_i)^2}{4} - \sum_{\{l \mid (i,j) \in \mathcal{E}_l\}} k_i k_j \sin^2(\alpha_i - \alpha_j)}$$

where $l \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|\}$ and \mathcal{E}_l represents edge l in \mathcal{G} .

For stability analysis, let us consider an autonomous system

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= -Ax + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dots & 0 & B \end{bmatrix}^\top y \\ \dot{y} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dots & 0 & C \end{bmatrix} x - Dy \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n, y \in \mathbb{R}^2, B, C, D \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ and are real symmetric matrices. In addition, $A + A^\top$ and D are positive definite.

Lemma 4.3: The system (4) is exponentially stable if $2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top) > \lambda_{\max}^2(B + C)\lambda_{\max}(D^{-1})$.

The proof follows from choosing $V(x, y) = x^\top x + y^\top y$ as a Lyapunov function and applying standard methodology from the state-space representation of linear systems.

1) *Interconnection merging into a stable formation with two coleaders:* Let us first focus on the case where the new agent merge to the formation of n -agent systems by establishing edges to two co-leader agents that are connected by a link. The two agents in the original network and the newly added agent can be equipped by either distance-based or bearing-only sensing mechanism, and each of them uses correspondingly the distance-based or bearing-only gradient

control law, respectively. As an example, we consider the n -agent systems as shown in Fig. 1 where the robot $R(n+1)$ will merge to the formation by establishing two edges to the coleader robots $R1$ and $R2$ that are already connected by the link $R2 \rightarrow R1$.

When the new-added agent is distance-based robot, following the formation graph in Fig. 1, one can obtain that the closed-loop dynamics of $(n+1)$ -agent systems is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_1 \\ \dot{p}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{p}_{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \frac{e_1^{\text{dist}} z_{12}}{2 \|z_{12}^*\|^2} + k_l \frac{e_l^{\text{dist}} z_{1,n+1}}{2 \|z_{1,n+1}^*\|^2} \\ k_2 \frac{e_2^{\text{dist}} z_{23}}{2 \|z_{23}^*\|^2} \\ \vdots \\ k_{l+1} \frac{e_{l+1}^{\text{dist}} z_{n+1,2}}{2 \|z_{n+1,2}^*\|^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $k_1 > 0$, $k_2 > 0$, $k_l > 0$ and $k_{l+1} > 0$ are the controller gains. Similarly, when the $R(n+1)$ robot is a bearing-only one, the control input of $R(n+1)$ will be bearing-only in (3). One can obtain all other cases when the robots $R1$ and $R2$ use different sensing mechanism, and when the link direction is reversed.

In the following proposition, we show that irrespective of the type of sensing mechanisms deployed in the two linked coleader agents from the original network and the sensor systems deployed by the new agent $R(n+1)$, we can design the controller gains such that the enlarged network can maintain a new formation shape. Without loss of generality, we denote the two coleader agents in the original network by $R1$ and $R2$.

Proposition 4.1: Consider the interconnection merging of robot $R(n+1)$ into a stable rigid formation of n heterogeneous agents with the given gains $k_1, \dots, k_{l+1} > 0$ by adding two links from/to two co-leader agents $R1$ and $R2$ with desired distance $d_{1,n+1}^*$, $d_{2,n+1}^*$ and/or desired bearing $g_{1,n+1}^*$, $g_{2,n+1}^*$. Let k_l and k_{l+1} be the control gains of the local gradient-based control law with k_l be the gain used by the agent from the original network and k_{l+1} be the gain used by the newly added agent. For any given $k_l = k_{l+1} > 0$, there exists $k_l^* > 0$ such that for all $k_l = k_{l+1} > k_l^*$ the newly formed $n+1$ minimally heterogeneous persistent formation system achieves local exponential stability.

In the following, we will prove the proposition for the case when $R(n+1)$ is a distance-based agent and the closed-loop system is given by (5). For all other cases, the proof follows a similar fashion.

In order to study the error dynamics, we analyse the dynamics of the edges that is given by the relative position vector z . For the original n -agent system, the closed-loop dynamics of relative position can be compactly described as

$$\dot{z} = f(z) \quad (6)$$

where $z = [\dots z_{ij}^T \dots]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2(|\mathcal{V}|-1)}$. Since by the hypothesis that the original n -agent forms an asymptotically stable rigid formation, the z -system above is locally asymptotically stable at an equilibrium point in $\mathcal{S} = \{z \in \mathbb{R}^{2(|\mathcal{V}|-1)} | z = z^*\}$.

This implies immediately that the linearization of (6) gives rise to

$$\dot{\hat{z}} = -A\hat{z} \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{z} = z - z^*$. In our iterative method, we can guarantee $A + A^T$ is positive definite. On the rigidity property of the new configuration, the added two links to the new agent ensures that the enlarged formation remains infinitesimally heterogeneous sensing rigid. This follows from the Henneberg insertion rule for maintaining graph rigidity.

Using (5), we can analyze the relative position of $(n+1)$ -agent system with state variables $z_m = [z^T z_{1,n+1}^T]^T$, where z is the relative position in the original formation framework.

Because the new added robot $R(n+1)$ only influence the relative position z_{21} in original n -agent system, we will focus on the interconnection that involves \dot{z}_{12} and $\dot{z}_{1,n+1}$ in the analysis part below. Consequently, we have the following dynamics of z_m

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{z}_{12} \\ \dot{z}_{1,n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ k_2 \frac{e_2^{\text{dist}} z_{23}}{2 \|z_{23}^*\|^2} - k_1 \frac{e_1^{\text{dist}} z_{12}}{2 \|z_{12}^*\|^2} - k_l \frac{e_l^{\text{dist}} z_{1,n+1}}{2 \|z_{1,n+1}^*\|^2} \\ k_{l+1} \frac{e_{l+1}^{\text{dist}} z_{n+1,2}}{2 \|z_{n+1,2}^*\|^2} - k_1 \frac{e_1^{\text{dist}} z_{12}}{2 \|z_{12}^*\|^2} - k_l \frac{e_l^{\text{dist}} z_{1,n+1}}{2 \|z_{1,n+1}^*\|^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

According to the edge relationship of triangle, $z_{n+1,2} = z_{12} - z_{1,n+1}$. The linearization of the closed-loop dynamics (8) at z_m^* yields

$$\dot{\hat{z}}_m = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{z}} \\ \dot{\hat{z}}_{1,n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -A \\ 0 \dots 0 C \\ 0 \dots 0 C -D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{z} \\ \hat{z}_{1,n+1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where $B = -k_l P_l$, $C = k_{l+1} P_{l+1} - k_l P_l$ and $D = k_{l+1} P_{l+1} + k_l P_l$ with P_l, P_{l+1}, P_1 be the projection matrices as defined before Lemma 4.1 and $\alpha_1 = \angle z_{12}^*$, $\alpha_l = \angle z_{1,n+1}^*$, $\alpha_{l+1} = \angle z_{n+1,2}^*$. According to Lemma 4.3, the system (IV-1) is exponential stable if $2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^T) > \lambda_{\max}^2(B + C)\lambda_{\max}(D^{-1})$. Based on Lemma 4.1, D^{-1} is given by

$$D^{-1} = \frac{1}{k_l k_{l+1} \sin^2 \theta_1} (\bar{v}_l \bar{v}_l^T + \bar{v}_{l+1} \bar{v}_{l+1}^T), \quad (10)$$

where $\theta_1 = \alpha_l - \alpha_{l+1}$, \bar{v}_l and \bar{v}_{l+1} are defined before Lemma 4.1. Additionally, Lemma 4.2 shows that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{\max}(D^{-1}) &= \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta_1}}{k_l k_{l+1} \sin^2 \theta_1} \\ \lambda_{\max}(B + C) &= \frac{k_1 + k_l - k_{l+1}}{2} + \\ &\quad \sqrt{\left(\frac{k_1 + k_l - k_{l+1}}{2}\right)^2 + k_l k_{l+1} \sin^2 \theta_1 + k_1 k_{l+1} \sin^2 \theta_2 - k_1 k_l \sin^2 \theta_3} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\theta_2 = \alpha_1 - \alpha_{l+1}$ and $\theta_3 = \alpha_1 - \alpha_l$. Since the desired positions of agents are noncollinear, it implies that $\sin \theta_1 \neq 0$, $\sin \theta_2 \neq 0$ and $\sin \theta_3 \neq 0$. For any given $k_l = k_{l+1}$, $2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^T) > \lambda_{\max}^2(B + C)\lambda_{\max}(D^{-1})$ can be given by

$$2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^T)(1 - \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta_1}) > f^2(\mu) \quad (12)$$

where $\mu = \frac{k_1}{k_l} > 0$, $f(\mu) = \frac{\mu}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\mu}{2}\right)^2 + \mu(\sin^2 \theta_2 - \sin^2 \theta_3) + \sin^2 \theta_1}$ and $f(\mu)$ is

Fig. 2. Interconnection merging into a stable formation with one leader

continuous and continuously differentiable. Since $f(\mu) > 0$, $\lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} f(\mu) = |\sin \theta_1|$, $\lim_{\mu \rightarrow +\infty} f(\mu) = +\infty$, according to the differential property of $f(\mu)$, we can derive that $f(\mu) > |\sin \theta_1|$ or there exists a unique minimum point $0 < \tilde{\mu} < 2(\sin^2 \theta_2 - \sin^2 \theta_3)$ where $f(\tilde{\mu}) < |\sin \theta_1|$. Since

$$\begin{aligned} 2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top)(1 - \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta_1}) &> \sin^2 \theta_1 \\ \Leftrightarrow 2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top) &> 1 + \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta_1}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

we can conclude that if $2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top) > 1 + \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta_1}$ holds then there exists $\tilde{\mu} > 0$ such that $2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top)(1 - \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta_1}) > f(\mu)$ holds for all $\mu < \tilde{\mu}$. We know the inequality (13) can be readily met by augmenting the gains within the existing system using the same multiplier. It shows that for all $k_l = k_{l+1} > \frac{k_1}{\tilde{\mu}}$, we have that $2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top) > \lambda_{\max}^2(B + C)\lambda_{\max}(D^{-1})$. By the application of Lemma 4.3, the augmented system is exponentially stable.

2) *Interconnection merging into a stable formation with one leader:* Here we focus on the $n + 1$ agents case in which n heterogeneous sensing agents are able to form a one-leader minimally heterogeneous persistent formation with local stability while another agent is merging into such stable formation of n -agent systems. As an illustration, let us consider the case where two distance-based robots $R1$ and $R2$ are connected by a link where $R1$ is the leader of the formation. The merging robot $R(n + 1)$ can be equipped with distance or bearing-only sensor system. Figure 2 shows an example of the graph where the merging robot $R(n + 1)$ can be detected by the leader $R1$ while the robot $R2$ can be detected by $R(n + 1)$; hence they form an interconnected systems among themselves.

When $R(n + 1)$ is a distance-based robot, the closed-loop dynamics of $(n + 1)$ -agent system is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_1 \\ \dot{p}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{p}_{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} k_l \frac{e_l^{\text{dist}}}{2\|z_{1,n+1}^*\|^2} z_{1,n+1} \\ k_1 \frac{e_1^{\text{dist}}}{2\|z_{21}^*\|^2} z_{21} + k_2 \frac{e_2^{\text{dist}}}{2\|z_{23}^*\|^2} z_{23} \\ \vdots \\ k_{l+1} \frac{e_{l+1}^{\text{dist}}}{2\|z_{n+1,2}^*\|^2} z_{n+1,2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where $k_1 > 0$, $k_2 > 0$, $k_l > 0$ and $k_{l+1} > 0$ are the controller gains. Similarly, if $R(n + 1)$ is a bearing-only robot, the control input of $R(n + 1)$ will be bearing-only in (3). For other cases when the robots $R1$ and $R2$ use different sensing mechanism, we can obtain similar expressions as above.

In the following proposition, we show that irrespective of the type of sensing mechanisms deployed in the one leader

agent from the original network and the sensor systems deployed by the new agent $R(n + 1)$, we can design the controller gains such that the enlarged network can maintain a new formation shape. Without loss of generality, we denote the one leader agent in the original network by $R1$.

Proposition 4.2: Consider the interconnection merging of robot $R(n + 1)$ into a stable rigid formation of n heterogeneous agents with the given gains $k_1, \dots, k_{l-1} > 0$ by adding one link from the leader agent $R1$ to $R(n + 1)$ and another link from $R(n + 1)$ to $R2$ with desired distance $d_{1,n+1}^*$, $d_{2,n+1}^*$ and/or desired bearing $g_{1,n+1}^*$, $g_{2,n+1}^*$. Let k_l be the gain for the distributed control law on the link $R1 \rightarrow R(n + 1)$ and k_{l+1} be the gain for the distributed control law on the link $R(n + 1) \rightarrow R2$. For any given $k_l = k_{l+1} > 0$, the newly formed $n + 1$ minimally heterogeneous persistent formation system achieves local exponential stability.

In the following, we will prove the proposition for the case when $R(n + 1)$ is a distance-based agent and the closed-loop system is given by (14). For all other cases, the proof follows vis-à-vis.

Following the same process in the proof of Proposition 4.1, the linearization of the closed-loop relative position dynamics at desired relative positions yields

$$\dot{\hat{z}}_m = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{z}} \\ \dot{\hat{z}}_{1,n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -A & 0 \\ \vdots & \dot{B} \\ 0 \dots 0 & C & -D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{z} \\ \hat{z}_{1,n+1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

where $B = -k_l P_l$, $C = k_{l+1} P_{l+1}$ and $D = (k_l P_l + k_{l+1} P_{l+1})$ with the projection matrices P_l, P_{l+1} and $\alpha_l = \mathcal{L}z_{1,n+1}^*$, $\alpha_{l+1} = \mathcal{L}z_{n+1,2}^*$. In addition, D and $A + A^\top$ are both positive definite.

Note that following Lemma 4.3, the system (15) is exponential stable if $2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top) > \lambda_{\max}^2(B + C)\lambda_{\max}(D^{-1})$. Following the same computation as in the proof of Proposition 4.1, we can arrive at the following sufficient condition

$$2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top) > \frac{\left(\frac{k_l - k_{l+1}}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{k_l - k_{l+1}}{2}\right)^2 + k_l k_{l+1} \sin^2 \theta}\right)^2}{k_l k_{l+1} \sin^2 \theta} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta}\right), \quad (16)$$

where $\theta = \alpha_l - \alpha_{l+1}$. By assumption, $\sin(\alpha_l - \alpha_{l+1}) \neq 0$ because the desired positions of agents are noncollinear. Since $k_l = k_{l+1}$ by the hypothesis of the proposition, the inequality (16) becomes

$$2\lambda_{\min}(A + A^\top) > 1 + \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta}. \quad (17)$$

The preceding inequality can be readily met by augmenting the gains within the existing system using the same multiplier. We prove the claim.

3) *Unilateral-connection merging into a stable formation:* Finally, we focus on the case C2 on the unilateral-connection merging for $n + 1$ agents. Similar to the setup in the previous case, it is assumed that there are n heterogeneous sensing agents which are able to form a minimally heterogeneous persistent formation with local stability. In contrast to the previous case, the new robot $R(n + 1)$ will merge to such stable formation by establishing two links unilaterally to any agents in the n -agent systems.

Fig. 3. Unilateral-connection merging into a stable formation

Without loss of generality, we label the two agents where robot $R(n+1)$ establishes the new links by $R1$ and $R2$, respectively. Figure 3 shown an example of the graph where the merging robot $R(n+1)$ equipped with distance sensor system can detect $R1$ and $R2$. In this case, when $R(n+1)$ is a distance-based robot, the dynamics of the closed-loop system is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \dot{p}_{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ k_l \frac{e_l^{\text{dist}}}{2 \|z_{n+1,1}^*\|^2} z_{n+1,1} + k_{l+1} \frac{e_{l+1}^{\text{dist}}}{2 \|z_{n+1,2}^*\|^2} z_{n+1,2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where $k_l > 0$ and $k_{l+1} > 0$ are the controller gains. Similarly, if $R(n+1)$ is a bearing-only robot, the control input of $R(n+1)$ will be bearing-only in (3).

The following proposition shows that independent of the type of sensing mechanism in the three robots $R1$, $R2$ and $R(n+1)$, we can design the controller gains k_l and k_{l+1} such that the new formation is stable.

Proposition 4.3: Consider the unilateral connection merging of robot $R(n+1)$ into a stable rigid formation of n heterogeneous agents with the given gains $k_1, \dots, k_{l-1} > 0$ by adding two links to the agents $R1$ and $R2$, which are not collinear, with desired distance $d_{n+1,1}^*$, $d_{n+1,2}^*$ or desired bearing $g_{n+1,1}^*$, $g_{n+1,2}^*$. Let k_l, k_{l+1} be the gains for the distributed control laws on the links $R(n+1) \rightarrow R1$ and $R(n+1) \rightarrow R2$, respectively. For any given $k_l, k_{l+1} > 0$, the newly formed $n+1$ minimally heterogeneous persistent formation system achieves local exponential stability.

In the following, we will prove the proposition for the case when $R(n+1)$ is a distance-based agent and the closed-loop system is given by (18). For the case when $R(n+1)$ is a bearing-only agent, the proof follows similarly.

Following the same process in the proof of Proposition 4.1, the linearization of the closed-loop relative-position dynamics at desired relative positions yields

$$\dot{\hat{z}}_m = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{z}} \\ \dot{\hat{z}}_{n+1,1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -A & 0 \\ * & -D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{z} \\ \hat{z}_{n+1,1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

where $B = -k_l P_l$, $C = k_{l+1} P_{l+1}$ and $D = (k_l P_l + k_{l+1} P_{l+1})$ with the projection matrices P_l, P_{l+1} and $\alpha_l = \angle z_{1,n+1}^*$, $\alpha_{l+1} = \angle z_{n+1,2}^*$. Because $-A$ is Hurwitz and $-D$ are negative definite, we can conclude the system (19) is globally exponentially stable. This implies that (18) is locally asymptotically stable at desired relative positions.

(a) First merging case: a bearing-only agent $R3$ and a distance-based agent $R4$ join the 2-agent formation systems
 (b) Second merging case: a bearing-only agent $R5$ and a distance-based agent $R6$ join the 4-agent formation systems

Fig. 4. Underlying graphs of formation system in simulation

V. SIMULATION

A. Simulation setup

In this subsection, we present simulation setup for 6-agent heterogeneous sensing formation that is formed by merging two extra agent at-a-time. The merging process incorporates all the different merging cases described in the previous section, where we start from two agent systems and it is expanded to 6-agent system. The different merging cases in this setup are summarized in Figure 4. For the desired formation, we set the distance and bearing constraints as $\{d_{12}^* = 5, g_{21}^* = [1, 0]^\top, d_{13}^* = 5\sqrt{2}, g_{23}^* = [0, -1]^\top, g_{34}^* = [-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}]^\top, d_{42}^* = 5, d_{45}^* = 5, g_{52}^* = [\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}]^\top, d_{61}^* = 5, d_{62}^* = 5\sqrt{2}\}$.

B. Simulation results

In this part, we present simulation results of various the merging processes from 2-agent heterogeneous formation towards 6-agent heterogeneous formation as described before.

After scaling up, the closed-loop dynamics is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_1 \\ \dot{p}_2 \\ \dot{p}_3 \\ \dot{p}_4 \\ \dot{p}_5 \\ \dot{p}_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \frac{e_1^{\text{dist}} z_{12}}{2 \|z_{12}^*\|^2} + k_2 \frac{e_2^{\text{dist}} z_{13}}{2 \|z_{13}^*\|^2} \\ k_3 \|z_{21}^*\| e_1^{\text{bearing}} + k_4 \|z_{23}^*\| e_2^{\text{bearing}} \\ k_5 \|z_{34}^*\| e_3^{\text{bearing}} \\ k_6 \frac{e_3^{\text{dist}} z_{42}}{2 \|z_{42}^*\|^2} + k_7 \frac{e_4^{\text{dist}} z_{45}}{2 \|z_{45}^*\|^2} \\ k_8 \|z_{56}^*\| e_4^{\text{bearing}} \\ k_9 \frac{e_5^{\text{dist}} z_{61}}{2 \|z_{61}^*\|^2} + k_{10} \frac{e_6^{\text{dist}} z_{62}}{2 \|z_{62}^*\|^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

where $k_1 = k_3 = 3$ as control gains of original two agents, the desired positive constants, such as $\|z_{56}^*\|$, are determined by the inter-agent distances of the desired shape. Following the computations in the proof of Proposition 4.1, the lower bound for k_2 and k_4 are given by $k_2^* = \frac{12\sqrt{3}}{23}$. For our selection, we opt for $k_2 = k_4 = 3$. In accordance with Proposition 4.2, we can choose any $k_5 = k_6 > 0$. To ensure a similar convergence rate, we set $k_5 = k_6 = 3$. Employing the same computations, we derive the lower bound of k_7 and k_8 as 3.695 and determine that k_9 and k_{10} can be any positive number. Accordingly, we set $k_7 = k_8 = 3.8$ and $k_9 = k_{10} = 3$. In the simulation, all gains are set as mentioned, and the result is shown in Figure

Fig. 5. Robot trajectories for the 6-agent heterogeneous sensing formation system setup; (■, ■, ■, ■, ■, ■) = (R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R6), ○ represents the initial and * is the final position. We have an initial configuration (dashed lines) where robots converge to the correct formation shape (solid lines) in every step.

5(c). It can be seen from this figure that the six-agent formation system is able to maintain the desired formation shape.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In the current work, we have considered the formation control problem in which agents have heterogeneous sensing mechanism, distance-based or bearing-only. Using heterogeneous sensing rigidity framework for defining the desired shape and using the persistence notion for heterogeneous sensing formation, we study the use of gradient-based control law for achieving the desired formation with heterogeneous sensing information. The distributed heterogeneous control design and analysis start from a core team of agents that can maintain the formation and it is scaled up by adding an agent one-at-a-time to the network. Simulation results show the validity of the theoretical results.

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